

Extraction of Mango Kernel Oil By Traditional Method of Ayurveda And Its Effect on The Shelf-Life of Mango

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Abstract Mango fruit is one of the important fruit crop in tropical and subtropical regions. The experiment was carried out to investigate the effect of mango kernel oil on the shelf life and colour development of mango cultivar Langra and also the extraction of kernel oil by Ayurvedic method. Vidhyadhar yantra was used for the extraction of oil. Extracted oil is treated with raw mango fruit with three dosages (10%, 20%, 30%). All the treated fruits remain green upto 6 days of storage. The maximum delay ripening was recorded in fruits treated with 30% kernel oil.

Keywords Mango Kernel Oil, Shelf Life, Vidhyadhar Yantra, Mango.

Introduction

Plant is one of the nature's best gift to men given by God but its full potential may not be utilized. Mango seed residue is one of them. Mango seed is discarded by juice manufacturing industry as well as by all the consumers of mango fruit. The alternative use of mango fruit is very important. After consumption or industrial processing of mangoes, approximately 40 to 60 % waste is generated during processing of mangoes; 12 to 15 % consists of peels and 15 to 20 % of kernels. According to mango varieties, the seed represents from 10 to 25 % of the whole fruit weight. The kernels inside the seed represents from 45 to 75% of the seed and about 20% of the whole fruit. However, more than one million tons of mango seeds are being treated as waste (Karunanithi *et al.* 2015). Mango (*Mangifera indica*) belongs to family Anacardiaceae which comprises more than 70 genera. Historical records suggest that its cultivation as a fruit originated in India more than 4000 years ago (Mukherjee S K 1998). Mango is one of the choicest fruit crop of tropical and subtropical region of the world especially in Asia. Its popularity and importance can easily be realized by the fact that it is often referred as 'King of Fruits' in the tropical world (Singh *et al.* 2002). Mango production is however quite concentrated since Asia accounts for approximately 77% of global mango production and America and Africa account for the remaining 23% (FAOSTAT 2007). Mango is affected by a number of disease at all the stages of the development. Among the disease most destructive disease is anthracnose which is caused by *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*.

Objective of study

In the present research there was an ancient method used to extract the oil from mango seed kernel and used the oil to investigate its effect on the mango fruits. This method is easier for extraction of oil for farmers. The research was conducted in Department of Botany C.C.S University Meerut. The research was to investigate the effect of mango kernel oil in controlling the post harvest anthracnose disease caused by *Colletotrichum* sp. And also evaluate its effect on ripening of fruits.

Review of Literature

A huge number of mango fruit is spoiled each year due to lack of proper storage and handling. Hence adequate measures should be taken to increase the shelf life of mangoes. Proper storage is necessary to increase the shelf life and prevent the fruits from disease because the mangoes transported to a long distances. Thus the prolong storage life of fruit consisting in slowing down the ripening process of mango fruit.

Application of synthetic chemical for prevention of post harvest disease is at present being misused .The use of essential oils for the control of disease has become an alternative to synthetic chemicals due to its therapeutic activity and toxicity to fungi, bacteria and insects.(Delespaul *et al.*, 2000)

Anthrachnose of mango has been effectively controlled by the use of essential oils, ginger and cinnamon.(Sefu *et al.*, 2015) and lemon grass (Duam Khanmane 2008).Abd –alla and Haggag (2013) reported that basil oil, orange oil and mustard oil has been effective in controlling the anthrachnose of mangoes.

Abeywickrama *et al.*, (2003) ,Anthony *et al.*, (2004), Anthony *et al.*, (2003) carried out a extensive work in Srilanka on the use of essential oils for the control of post harvest disease of banana fruit.

Cardamon oil in warm water (45 °C) used as a dip treatment in vivo , significantly reduced stem -end rot development in mango cultivar karuthacolomban investigated by Kulasinghe *et al.*, in 2019.

Kodituwakku *et al.*, (2020) gives spray and fumigation treatment with basil , clove , cinnamon, leaf and cinnamon bark oils effectively controlled stem-end rot in mango cultivar Karthocolomban stored at 12- 14°C.

The essential oils are more effective due to their high volatile nature and they can be used as a coating material to slowdown the ripening process and protects the fruits from water loss and spoilage.(Antunesa *et al.*, 2012)

To protect fruits from the spoilage we should apply adequate post harvest technologies such as hot water treatment, stored in polythene bags, stored in low temperature i.e. refrigeration at different low temperature, paper wrapping , plastic films for atmospheric modification etc.

Mohd Zafrul Hasan (2020) investigate the use of different oil to reduce the fruit decay and increase the shelf life of mango fruit he had used the coating of paraffin, almond oil, olive oil, sesame oil, coconut oil and mustard oil and they found that almond oil and paraffin coating gave the best result in reduction of disease, reduction of weight loss and firmness respectively, which resulted prolonged shelf life of mango.

Main Text

Properties of mango kernel oil

Mango seed kernel, hitherto considered as waste, contain substantial levels of health-enhancing compounds and natural antioxidants (Abdel –Aty *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, more than one million tons of mango seeds are being treated as waste, subsequently leading to environmental pollution. However, with appropriate treatment and study, the kernel (seeds) might be possibly used as a food ingredient, medicine and many other purposes (Abdullah *et al.*, 2011).Mango seed kernel oil has been shown to have high antibacterial activity, supports the development of the placenta and fetus, and helps in the metabolic activities of teeth, the retina and the skin, while preventing anemia. In addition, it also helps to tighten the capillary vessels and can be used as nutrient rich food oil or as ingredients for functional or enriched foods (Kittiphoom And Sutasinee 2013). Mango chemicals is hoped to promote research into its potential as a novel antibacterial against pathogenic micro- organism and the allied application (Abdullah et al 2011).Among the rural folks the mango kernels are used traditionally as antimicrobials against gastric pathogens especially for the infants. (Asemave *et al.*, 2020). Mango kernel produces 12- 15 % edible oil, studies have disclosed that mango kernel is a potential source of wide range of bioactive compounds and antioxidants (Jafari *et al.*, 2014).

Kernel oil composition

Olagunju Esther Olajumoke (2013) reported the proximate analysis and physiochemical analysis of mango kernel oil (Table 1 & 2).

Table- 1 Proximate composition of *M.indica* seed

Parameter	Value %
Ash	2.82
Moisture content	19.80
Ether extract	25.57
Crude protein	6.58
Crude fibre	4.69
Carbohydrate	40.50

Table- 2 Physiochemical characteristics of oil from *M.indica*

Parameters	Value %
Oil contents(%)	25.57±.10
Peroxide value (millieq/kg)	1.20± 0.05
Acid value (mg/100g)	16.28±0.10
Saponification value (mgKOH/100g)	71.52±0.10
FFA (mg/100g)	8.17±0.05
Iodine value (gl2 /100g)	5.58±0.05
Refractive Index	1.45±0.05

Methodology

For extraction of oil from mango kernel an Ayurvedic Yantra is used which is called as Vidhyadhar Yantra. Traditionally this apparatus is used to extract mercury from cinnabar etc. (Ras Raj Sundar).

About the apparatus:-First of all we take a pot and place a bowl in the pot and spread the small pieces of mango kernel around the bowl and put the another pot on the first one pot and joined the both pot with the mud and cloth around the joint of both pot and let it dry in shade.After one night the apparatus is placed on the gas stove and filled the upper pot with cold water.After heating if the vapour comes out from the joint of the pots apply two and three coat of mud and let it dry again for 2- 4 hours.After drying the mud the Apparatus is put on the gas stove for 2-3 hours.The second pot which contain cold water becomes hot after sometime. We replace the hot water with cold water After three hours the gas will off and cool the apparatus.After cooling the apparatus separate the first pot from second pot very carefully. The condensed oil is dropped into the bowl. Filter the oil and used it for further study.

Mango fruit were collected from the department of Botany CCS University Meerut. Raw and green fruits were harvested with similar shape and size. Harvested fruits were washed with water to remove the dust and sterilized with ethanol . Sterilized fruits were sprayed with 0, 10%, 20%, 30% kernel oil and kept in sterilized polythene bags. Treated and untreated fruits were kept at room temperature. Shelf life was determined by counting the date from harvested to its last edible stage and was expressed in day.

Sampling

Mango seed were collected from the juice manufacturing market .The mango seeds were sun dried for 10 days and decoated the seed mechanically and separate the kernel .The kernel of mango seed were break into small pieces.

Analysis

Dry mango kernels.

Lower pot with mango kernels

Lower pot with mango kernel and Bowl

Vidhyadhar yantra

Extracted oil

Table 3: Effect of mango kernel oil on shelf life of mango fruits

Cultivar	Amount of oil (%)	Days of storage					
		0	3	6	9	12	15
Langra	Treatments						
	Control	Raw	Raw	Ripened	Rotting	Rotting	Rotting
	10%	Raw	Raw	60% ripened	Over ripened	Rotting	Rotting
	20%	Raw	Raw	70% ripened	Complete ripened	Rotting start	Rotting
	30%	Raw	Raw	50% ripened	Complete ripened but remain fresh	Over ripening	Rotting

Table 4: Show the development of colour as affected by the mango kernel oil

Cultivar	Amount of oil (%)	Day of Storage					
		0	3	6	9	12	15
Langra	Treatments						
	Control	Green	Green	TY	--	--	--
	10%	Green	Green	Green	TY	--	--
	20%	Green	Green	Green	TY	--	--
	30%	Green	Green	Green	Green		

TY- Trace of yellow colour

Images show the effect of mango kernel oil after 6 days of treatment.

Result and Discussion

The oil extracted by ancient method have a black colour and have smell. However this is decidedly a more tedious and time consuming method. Only disadvantage is that it is slightly turbid. This oil is filtered and placed in bottle for further study. The oil is used to observe the effect on the shelf life of mango.

Mango kernel oil had a little effect on the colour development of mango fruits. All the treated fruits remain green up to 6 days of treatment. Untreated control fruits became unfit after 6 days of treatment the fruit start rotting from the tip. The fruits treated with 10% kernel oil had over ripened after six days. The fruits treated with 20% kernel oil were ripened 70% and fruits treated with 30% oil were ripened 60% after six days of treatment. The maximum delay (9 days) in ripening was recorded in fruits treated with 30% kernel oil. Control fruit ripened after 5 days and on the 6 day fruit shows over ripening and rotting from tip. Fruits treated with 20% were ripened 90% on the seventh day 80% fruits were ripened which treated with 30% kernel oil. 20% and 30% fruits were ripened 100% on 8 days. The fruits treated with 20% oil shows rotting from the tip on the ninth day while fruits remain fresh which treated with 30% kernel oil.

Essential oils of basil, lemon, orange and mustard are used to reduce post harvest losses of mango by *C.gloeosporioides* (Abd-Alla and Haggag 2013). According to Sharma (2014) coating of individual mango with coconut oil, mustard oil, deshi ghee and natural wax are used to protect the fruit from many post harvest pathogens. The oils are smeared on the surface of the fruit with cotton swab. After coating, fruits should be air dried and stored at room temperature in pierced brown bags for 7 days.

Danh (2021) used essential oil of cinnamon, basil, lemongrass, peppermint, coriander, and orange to control of anthracnose disease caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* on the post harvest mangoes of cat hoa loc variety.

The results revealed that mango kernel oil delayed ripening of the fruits treated with 30% mango kernel oil. The study indicates that shelf-life of the treated fruits were extended with help of mango kernel oil. Mango kernel oil is also helpful to inhibit the growth of microbes for this further investigation is necessary which researcher continued in her research.

Conclusion

Mango fruits treated with mango kernel oil had very little effect on the colour development but delayed ripening as compared to untreated control effected the self-life of mango fruits. In developing nation we used a variety of chemical fungicides to destroy the microbes but these fungicides are not eco-friendly with our environment. They are hazardous so I want to find out the alternative of these fungicides to enable the growth of microbes in my research. I want to use mango kernel oil to inhibit the growth of microbes.

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